

ISic2703

I.Sicily inscription 2703

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea"

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334292

1. Θεοφίλας.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645123

PHI 334292

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le

iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 190
Calderone, S. 1949. Analecta epigraphica liparensia. *Epigraphica*. 11: 49-60. At
50 no.2

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2703. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387291>